

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

STAKEHOLDER FORUM

TABLE OF CONTENT

<i>Session 1 : Exchange session</i>	6
WORKSHOP: ORGANIC ANIMAL HUSBANDRY SYSTEMS– CHALLENGES, PERFORMANCE, POTENTIALS AND RESEARCH NEEDS - IAHA PRE-CONFERENCE RECOMMENDATIONS	6
<i>Session 2 : Exchange session</i>	7
ENGAGEMENT.BIOBREEDING - WHY WE NEED TO INTEGRATE PLANT AND ANIMAL BREEDING INTO THE ORGANIC VALUE CHAIN?	7
<i>Session 3 : Exchange session</i>	8
CONSUMERS AND CITIES AS “CO-PRODUCERS” - CHANGEMAKERS FOR THE AGRICULTURAL PARADIGM SHIFT TO ORGANIC	8
<i>Session 4 : Exchange session</i>	9
HOW FAR CAN ORGANIC FOOD AND FARMING DEVELOP?	9
<i>Session 5 : Exchange session</i>	10
TASTE THE INNOVATION OF SEED AMBASSADORS	10
<i>Session 6 : Exchange session</i>	11
WHICH NATURAL INPUTS DO WE NEED IN ORGANIC FARMING SYSTEMS? – DISCUSSING THE FUTURE OF PLANT PROTECTION PRODUCTS, FERTILISERS AND INPUTS FOR LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION	11
<i>Session 7: Exchange session</i>	12
ORGANIC FOOD SYSTEMS BUILT ON PLANT-BASED INNOVATIONS – CAN WE MAKE IT HAPPEN?.....	12
<i>Session 8: Exchange session</i>	13
THE IMPACT OF GENETIC ENGINEERING ON THE WORLD... AND ON ORGANIC FARMING	13
<i>Session 10: Territorial scale</i>	14
ACCESS TO LAND, AS CORNERSTONE OF ORGANIC LOCAL FOOD AND FARMING SYSTEMS	14
FERTILIZATION WITH RECYCLED NUTRIENTS IN ORGANIC FARMING FOOD SYSTEM	15
DOES ORGANIC FARMING MATTER FOR IMPROVED WATER PRODUCTIVITY AND CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURE? A CASE OF WATER-EFFICIENT AND ORGANIC RICE AND COTTON BUSINESS AND INNOVATION.....	16
PARMA BIO-DISTRICT FOR TERRITORY DEVELOPMENT: A STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS	17
AN INNOVATION LABORATORY ON A WINE TERRITORY IN GIRONDE: WHAT ARE THE ECONOMIC, ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL IMPACTS OF ORGANIC FARMING ON THIS TERRITORY?	18
<i>Session 11: Exchange session</i>	19
FIRST ORGANIC COFFEE PROJECT IN BURUNDI AND HOW TO MAINSTREAM THE ADOPTION OF AGROFORESTRY SYSTEMS IN COFFEE PRODUCTION	19

Session 12: Knowledge and innovation.....	20
"PUBLISH OR PERISH" – INTENSIFYING AND QUALIFYING SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE RESEARCH (ISO FAR)	20
OVERCOMING SOCIO-TECHNICAL LOCK-INS OF ORGANIC CEREAL PRODUCTION IN EUROPE: HOW TO FOSTER AND SUSTAIN MULTI-ACTOR GRASSROOTS INITIATIVES AS DRIVERS OF TRANSITION	21
A SERIOUS-GAME TO FOSTER TRANSITION TO SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS REGARDING SOIL HEALTH MANAGEMENT BASED ON A PROVENCAL MARKET GARDENING CASE STUDY	22
EXTENSION AND ADVISORY SERVICE NEEDS OF STARTUPS AND ESTABLISHED ORGANIC FARMERS IN INDIA-THE CHALLENGES AND WAYFORWARD	23
WHICH TRICKS FOR DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR ORGANIC PRODUCTION.....	24
Session 13: Exchange session	25
ORGANIC AQUACULTURE	25
Session 14: Exchange session	26
SHARED SURVEILLANCE AND REGIONAL ADAPTIVENESS UNDER INTERNATIONAL ORGANIC STANDARDS	26
Session 15: Exchange session	27
CORE ORGANIC NETWORK: 15 YEARS OF EUROPEAN TRANSNATIONAL RESEARCH IN ORGANIC FOOD AND FARMING.....	27
Session 16: Exchange session	28
CERTIFICATION AS A GROUP OF OPERATORS IN EUROPE: REQUIREMENTS, BEST PRACTICE AND CHALLENGES.....	28
Session 17: Exchange session	29
HOW TO INCREASE PRODUCTION AND USE OF ORGANIC SEED? STATE OF THE ART AND BEST PRACTICES	29
Session 18: Exchange session	30
HOW REGIONAL KNOWLEDGE HUBS DISSEMINATE VALIDATED KNOWLEDGE ON ORGANIC AGRICULTURE APPLYING A MULTI STAKEHOLDER APPROACH.....	30
Session 19: Certification	31
SHARING THE OUTCOMES OF THE PRE-CONFERENCE "30 YEARS OF PGS DEVELOPMENT: A ROOT AND BRANCH APPRAISAL"	31
LE SYSTÈME PARTICIPATIF DE GARANTIE AU BÉNIN APRÈS CINQ ANNÉES DE MISE EN OEUVRE: ÉTATS DES LIEUX ET PERSPECTIVES	32
ORGANIC CERTIFICATION IS EXPELLING SMALL PRODUCERS FROM THE MARKET?	33
ORGANIC PASIFIKA CERTIFICATION, LEVERAGING FOR ENHANCED RESILIENCE	34
ORGANIC FOOD INTEGRITY & AUTHENTICITY: A KEY CHALLENGE FOR SUSTAINABLE GROWTH	35
Session 20: Genetic diversity.....	36
DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE SEED SYSTEMS FOR ORGANIC FARMING	36
BRESOV (2018-2022): A EUROPEAN PROJECT DEDICATED TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF RESILIENT AND SUSTAINABLE ORGANIC VEGETABLE PRODUCTION (TOMATO, BROCCOLI, SNAP BEAN)	37
A COOPERATIVE ORIGINAL EXPERIENCE TO IMPROVE WINTER BREAD WHEAT ORGANIC BREEDING	

STRATEGIES	38
OLD PROBLEMS NEW SOLUTIONS: BROKERING AGROBIODIVERSITY MANAGEMENT ENTERPRISES IN CUBA	39
CO-DEVELOPMENT OF A PARTICIPATORY VARIETY TRIAL NETWORK FOR DIVERSIFIED ORGANIC VEGETABLE FARMERS	40
Session 21: Exchange session	41
CAPITALISING ON SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE TO EFFECTIVELY COMMUNICATE AND PROMOTE THE SUSTAINABILITY OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS	41
Session 25: Global and multi-actors.....	42
MILPA PROGRAM HOW A PARTNERSHIP BETWEEN A PRIVATE FOOD COMPANY & ORGANIC INSTITUTIONAL STAKEHOLDERS ACCELERATE DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC REGENERATIVE AGRICULTURE IN FRANCE	44
ORGANIC PROCESSING METHODS – THE WAY FORWARD	45
MINDFUL EATING: A FIRST STEP TOWARDS A HEALTHY FUTURE	46
Session 26: Network.....	47
THE ONLINE PLATFORM “ORGANIC FARM KNOWLEDGE”	47
THE FLEMISH ORGANIC RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGE (FORK)- NETWORK IN PRACTICE FARMERS AT THE HEART OF THE FLEMISH ORGANIC RESEARCH & KNOWLEDGE (FORK)- NETWORK.....	48
AGENCE BIO, A CONSULTATION PLATFORM FOR ALL ACTORS ON ALL ORGANIC ISSUES	49
KNOWLEDGE HUB FOR ORGANIC FOOD AND FARMING	50

STAKEHOLDER Board

- Vianney Le Pichon (ITAB, France)
- Stéphane Bellon (INRA, France)
- Philippe Baret (UCL, Belgium)
- Pauline Verrière (IFOAM EU group, Belgium)
- Fiona Marty (FNAB, France)
- Paola Migliorini (Agroecology Europe, Italy)
- Charles Pernin (SYNABIO, France)
- Louise Luttkholt (IFOAM - Organics International, Germany)
- Santiago Sarandon (SOCLA, South America)
- Million Belay (AFSA, Africa)
- Jennifer Chang (ALGOA, Asia)
- Judith Hitchman / Jocelyn Parot (Urgenci, France)

REVIEWERS

- Philippe BARET
- Stéphane BELLON
- Jennifer CHANG
- Vianney LE PICHON
- Paola MIGLIORINI
- Jocelyn PAROT
- Santiago SARANDON

PAPERS

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 3 - Develop organic and sustainable plant and animal production, food and non-food systems

Session 1 : Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-1210

WORKSHOP: ORGANIC ANIMAL HUSBANDRY SYSTEMS– CHALLENGES, PERFORMANCE, POTENTIALS AND RESEARCH NEEDS - IAHA PRE-CONFERENCE RECOMMENDATIONS

Otto Schmid¹, Marion Johnson², Mette Vaarst³, Catherine Everton⁴

¹FiBL, Wermatswil / Uster, Switzerland, ²Organic Research Centre, Newbury, United Kingdom,

³Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark, ⁴ITAB, Paris, France

Summary: The goal of the workshop is to discuss the conclusions and recommendations of the Pre-Conference on Organic Animal Husbandry systems, in collaboration with EU Core Organic projects, at the Organic World congress in September 2020.

Challenges, performance, and potentials will be summarised. Important development and research needs will be identified and discussed as well as policies for the further development of organic farming with animals towards sustainability.

Special attention is given to the future role of animals in sustainable food and farming systems. It is proposed that this workshop will be held in the Research Forum.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: organic animal husbandry, role of livestock, research needs, development

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 3 - Develop organic and sustainable plant and animal production, food and non-food systems

Session 2 : Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-1333

ENGAGEMENT.BIOBREEDING - WHY WE NEED TO INTEGRATE PLANT AND ANIMAL BREEDING INTO THE ORGANIC VALUE CHAIN?

Monika M. Messmer^{*1}, Micaela Colley², Freya Schaefer³, Miguel DePorras⁴ and ECO-PB

¹Crop Science, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL, Frick, Switzerland, ²Organic Seed Alliance OSA, Port Townsend, United States, ³Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL, Frankfurt, Germany, ⁴Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL, Brussel, Belgium

Summary: The organic sector is growing on a global scale. To guarantee the integrity of the organic value chain and to ensure future supply attention must be drawn to the source of our seeds and animal breeds. Most of them are derived from multi-national companies, focusing on industrialized agriculture and applying new genetic engineering techniques, which are not approved by the organic sector. Organic breeding initiatives offer an alternative for a self-determined development of the organic sector, but their financial basis is insufficient.

Integrating organic breeding into value chain partnerships and sharing responsibility among breeders, farmers, processors, retailers, traders and consumers is crucial for upscaling organic breeding and ensuring future food security, food quality and climate adaptation as well as integrity of the value chain.

In the workshop different actors will present case studies and debate about more integrated options of value chain partnerships for organic breeding.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: concerted action, integrity of supply chain, investment, organic breeding, value chain partnership

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

Session 3 : Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-1400

CONSUMERS AND CITIES AS “CO-PRODUCERS” - CHANGEMAKERS FOR THE AGRICULTURAL PARADIGM SHIFT TO ORGANIC

Bernward Geier*¹

¹COALBORA- Let's work together, Much, Germany

Summary: The session will explore the synergetic potential between farmers/producers and the countryside with consumers respectively “co-producers” in cities / urban areas. In this context there is a great potential in the context of public procurement. Very interesting developments like the most impressive case of the organic Food centre project in Copenhagen and lately a similar initiative Berlin will be show-cased. We will also look at the Food council movements in cities.

The session aims besides an exchange of information and update on the topic to explore strategies and needs to extend the success story of Copenhagen and the example of Berlin around the world. We are convinced, this is a strong tool to raise demand and give perspectives to farmers with fair prices.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Farmer –consumer cooperation, public procurement Organic food supply & catering Food councils

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 2 - Guide the growth dynamic of organics

Session 4 : Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-292

HOW FAR CAN ORGANIC FOOD AND FARMING DEVELOP?

Servane Penvern¹, Stephane Bellon¹, Marc Benoit², Cécile Detang-Dessendre³, Marc Tchamitchian¹, Françoise Médale⁴ and Steering committee of the INRA meta-program on organic food and farming scaling

¹Département Sciences pour l'action et le développement, INRA, Avignon, ²Département Sciences sociales, agriculture et alimentation, espace et environnement, INRA, Saint-Genès-Champanelle,

³Département Sciences sociales, agriculture et alimentation, espace et environnement, INRA, Dijon,

⁴Département Physiologie animale et systèmes d'élevage, INRA, Saint-Pee-sur-Nivelle, France

Summary: INRA is currently launching a new cross-cutting research program dedicated to the development of organic food systems. But how far can organic food and farming develop? Multiple scenarios are to be explored. With a participatory approach, this session aims to gather actors of the different worlds of the whole food system, all involved partly, fully, formerly or recently in organic scaling-up and scaling-out. It also aims at eliciting their different visions and viewpoints on the limitations and opportunities for a massive development of organic food and farming (OFF).

This brainstorming session will be synthesized live to address the multiplicity of scenarios and to highlight the lock-ins and drivers to explore. We assume that exchanges among stakeholders including researchers will provide useful insights on the necessary systemic and transdisciplinary approaches to contribute to organic food systems development and to set up priorities or an agenda.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Agri-food system, bottlenecks and drivers, development pathways, transition, Vision

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 5 - Foster biodiversity and diversity at multiple scales

Session 5 : Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-496

TASTE THE INNOVATION OF SEED AMBASSADORS

Edwin Nuijten¹, Monika Messmer^{*2}, Micaela Colley³, Véronique Chable⁴, Edith Lammerts van Bueren⁵, Pedro Mendes Moreira⁶, Adrian Rodriguez Burruezo⁷, Gabor Figeczky⁸

¹De Beersche Hoeve, Oostelbeers, Netherlands, ²FIBL, Frick, Switzerland, ³Organic Seed Alliance, Port Townsend, United States, ⁴INRA, Rennes, France, ⁵WUR, Wageningen, Netherlands, ⁶IPC, Coimbra, Portugal, ⁷UPV, Valencia, Spain, ⁸IFOAM international, Bonn, Germany

Summary: Maintaining diversity in seeds and plant breeding is important to the organic movement. This workshop will report in an interactive way on the outcomes of the preconference “Seed Ambassadors: building an international network to advance organic seed systems”. The workshop will consist of presentations, taste tests and world café sessions. The main message is that we are all part of the seed system and benefit from seed diversity and organic plant breeding. Presentations will be on:

- A systems-based breeding concept: broadening approaches in organic breeding
- Culinary breeding: celebrating a focus on taste, quality and food diversity
- Linking generations and cultures: supporting knowledge exchange and foster new developments

The participants will be actively engaged in developing a road map for the future, based on the concept of IFOAM 3.0, on issues like:

- Involvement of the value chain in plant breeding and financing thereof
- Creating seed networks
- Fostering diversity in breeding approaches

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: culinary breeding, cultural diversity, fostering diversity, new approaches, organic plant breeding, seed networks

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 3 - Develop organic and sustainable plant and animal production, food and non-food systems

Session 6 : Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-360

WHICH NATURAL INPUTS DO WE NEED IN ORGANIC FARMING SYSTEMS? – DISCUSSING THE FUTURE OF PLANT PROTECTION PRODUCTS, FERTILISERS AND INPUTS FOR LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION

Isabella Lang¹ on behalf of RELACS, Bram Moeskops², Lucius Tamm³ and RELACS - Improving inputs for organic farming

¹Policy Unit, ²Research Unit, IFOAM EU, Bruxelles, Belgium, ³Crop Sciences, FIBL, Frick, Switzerland

Summary: The RELACS project seeks to promote the development and adoption of environmentally friendly and economically viable tools and technologies to reduce the use of external, contentious inputs in organic farming systems. The proposed workshop aims at discussing the acceptability of certain natural inputs and alternative strategies to further reduce plant protection products, fertilisers and inputs for livestock.

The discussion will cover all major sectors of organic farming, including horticulture, arable cropping as well as livestock production. The diverse needs in different regions will be considered as well as the different opinions of farmers, consumers, advisors and researcher. It is expected that the use of some contentious inputs can be considerably reduced and roadmaps for gradually phasing out certain products such as, copper, mineral oils or antibiotics will be developed.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: feed additives, fertilisers, Natural inputs, plant protection products, veterinary medicinal products

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 2 - Guide the growth dynamic of organics

Session 7: Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-1041

ORGANIC FOOD SYSTEMS BUILT ON PLANT-BASED INNOVATIONS – CAN WE MAKE IT HAPPEN?

Maria Tunberg¹, Maria Wivstad¹, Rebecka Milestad¹, Karin Ullven¹

¹EPOK, Centre for Organic Food and Farming, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Uppsala, Sweden

Summary: A range of new plant-based products is currently being discussed, developed and introduced to the market. This is innovation in action and a process with potential to transform the organic food system as we know it today.

This process will affect the production and consumption of organic products but what are the key issues moving forward, and what can we learn from the innovations already in actions? In this session, we will bring together stakeholder from different parts of the organic food value chain. Together we will try to understand the process of innovation.

We will enable knowledge transfer and the creation of new contacts and collaborations. Hopefully we will even spark new innovative ideas in the field of organic plant-based products.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Food systems, Innovation, Plant-based products

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 6 - Commit together to the health of soils, food, people and of the planet

Session 8: Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-1089

THE IMPACT OF GENETIC ENGINEERING ON THE WORLD... AND ON ORGANIC FARMING

Eric Gall*¹ ¹IFOAM EU, Brussels, Belgium

Summary: Many new genetic engineering techniques have been developed in recent years, such as gene editing, with promises to "feed the world". In 2017, at the OWC in Delhi, India, the world organic movement adopted a position that makes it clear that such techniques are not compatible with the principles of organic farming, and that alternatives such as organic plant and animal breeding, should be pursued.

At the same time there is a global push from industry to deregulate these new techniques, so that traceability and the stricter standards that apply to GMOs in some regions of the world, do not apply.

What strategies should be followed to ensure that these new genetic engineering techniques will be regulated and that organic operators will have the tools to effectively exclude them from their production processes?

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: contamination, CRISPR/Cas9, gene editing, genetic engineering, Genetic modification, GMOs

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

Session 10: Territorial scale

OWC2020-STA-1233

ACCESS TO LAND, AS CORNERSTONE OF ORGANIC LOCAL FOOD AND FARMING SYSTEMS

Veronique Rioufol¹, Vratslava Janovska², Ruth Curtis³, Maarten ROELS⁴, Damien Roumet¹

¹Terre de Liens, Crest, France, ²AMPI & Nadaze Pro Pudu, Prague, Czech Republic, ³Soil Association and Soil Association Land Trust, Bristol, United Kingdom, ⁴Terre-en-vue, Brussels, Belgium

Summary: Farmland is the irreplaceable basis for food production. But competition for land, for both farming and non-farming uses, is on the rise. Increasingly, local actors have mobilised to develop local food and farming systems, ensuring quality local food, the transition towards organic farming, stronger rural communities, and a variety of short supply chains.

As they mobilise for local food and farming systems, local actors are faced with the issues of land preservation and land use. How to preserve farmland from non-farming uses and land loss? How to ensure that land is accessible and affordable to a new generation of organic farmers? How to ensure the continuity of farming and local farms despite the greying of farmers?

Over the past decade, local authorities and local stakeholders (organic associations, community land trusts, farm incubators, etc.) have developed a wide range of innovative approaches and tools towards mobilising land for organic farming and local organic food systems.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Land access; new entrants; local food systems; local food and farming; local authorities; social innovations

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 3 - Develop organic and sustainable plant and animal production, food and non-food systems

OWC2020-STA-1309

FERTILIZATION WITH RECYCLED NUTRIENTS IN ORGANIC FARMING FOOD SYSTEM

Jukka Kivelä¹, Päivi Kurki², Elina Nurmi²

¹Agricultural Sciences, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland, ²LUKE Natural Resources Institute Finland, Mikkeli

Summary: Fertilization in organic farming is based on recycling of nutrients. Yet, organic farming is also producing products which are brought out of the farm into the food industry and further into the food systems. The nutrients, which are not consumed as nutrition, need to be recycled.

Nutrients for recycling can be recovered in organic by products such as meat bone meal (MBM), they can be reused in the food system by using them as fertilizer in agricultural production.

It has been shown that meat bone meal fertilizer has a positive impact to the yield amount as well to the grain protein content in cereals. Same impact can be detected in other food industry has by-products used as fertilizers. Therefore, recycling fertilizers bring economic returns in form of higher yields. However, the nutrient recycling brings also environmental and social advantages. To make the these advantages a good practice in organic farming and in our food systems, we need to inform diverse stakeholders in our food systems.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: food industry by products, recycling nutrients, MBM, stakeholder co-operation

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 6 - Commit together to the health of soils, food, people and of the planet

OWC2020-STA-1337

DOES ORGANIC FARMING MATTER FOR IMPROVED WATER PRODUCTIVITY AND CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURE? A CASE OF WATER-EFFICIENT AND ORGANIC RICE AND COTTON BUSINESS AND INNOVATION

Stefanie Kaegi*¹ and Most probably additional authors will join, however, we have not yet defined who that will be.

¹Advisory Services, HELVETAS Swiss Intercooperation, Zurich, Switzerland

Summary: Agriculture uses 70% of the world's water. As the global population is increasing and the climate is changing, we are facing the growing threat of water and food shortages. The Water Productivity Project, short WAPRO, is a multi-stakeholder initiative to improve water efficiency in agriculture.

Organic agricultural practices are among the key means to increase water productivity and four of the ten WAPRO sub-projects adhere to a recognised organic standard for rice and cotton production. The session will focus on these four sub-projects.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Multistakeholder initiative, Organic Cotton, Organic rice , Water economies, Water productivity

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

OWC2020-STA-1370

PARMA BIO-DISTRICT FOR TERRITORY DEVELOPMENT: A STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS

Juan Pablo Sciarano*¹, Marianna Guareschi²

¹Rural Economy, ²Rural Development, Parma University, Parma, Italy

Summary: Bio- Districts or Eco-Regions represent a growing and innovative model of rural development in different European countries. Their goal is promoting sustainable development involving organic farmers' associations, local governments and other local stakeholders.

Parma, the capital of the "Food Valley", has been officially nominated a UNESCO "Creative City for gastronomy" is home to the largest organic cultivated area in Emilia Romagna.

Big food companies (e.g. Barilla, Parmalat, Mutti), small producers and food markets, rural festivals, and Solidarity Purchasing Groups all co-exist in the area representing different agricultural models.

On one hand, there is an intensive export-oriented agricultural model, and on the other, small farms oriented to preserve biodiversity and a direct relationship with consumers.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: bio regions, Organic 3.0, stakeholder survey

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

OWC2020-STA-830

AN INNOVATION LABORATORY ON A WINE TERRITORY IN GIRONDE: WHAT ARE THE ECONOMIC, ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL IMPACTS OF ORGANIC FARMING ON THIS TERRITORY?

Delhoume Marie*¹

¹INTERBIO Nouvelle-Aquitaine, BORDEAUX, France

Summary: The Laboratoire d'Innovation Territoriale Bio (LIT Bio) is part of the regional programme VITIREV «Innovons pour des territoires viticoles respectueux de l'environnement».

The objective of this project is to assess the impacts of organic agriculture on a territory on a cross-sector approach. To do this, participatory workshops involving all the people concerned in a given territory are mobilized: institutionals, professionals, civil society, associations, etc. Economic and environmental data are derived from partnerships with French agricultural development organizations and research centres.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: cross-sector, participatory workshops, pioneering wine-growing territories

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE

www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 3 - Develop organic and sustainable plant and animal production, food and non-food systems

Session 11: Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-1216

FIRST ORGANIC COFFEE PROJECT IN BURUNDI AND HOW TO MAINSTREAM THE ADOPTION OF AGROFORESTRY SYSTEMS IN COFFEE PRODUCTION

Manfred Fürst¹, Ernest Ndururaro^{*2}, Thomas Hoyer³, Heidi Megerle⁴, Anne Hessenland⁵

¹International Department, Naturland, Gräfelfing, Germany, ²General Manager, COCOCA, Bujumbura, Burundi, ³General Manager, WeltPartner, Ravensburg, ⁴Professur für Angewandte Geographie und Planung, Hochschule für Forstwirtschaft Rottenburg, Rottenburg am Neckar, Germany, ⁵International Department, Naturland, Moshi, Tanzania, United Republic of

Summary: A close cooperation of farmers, cooperative service units, other extension service suppliers, as well as governmental and non-governmental coffee institutions and bodies, marketing organizations and research institutions are cooperating to succeed and expand in the successful adoption of agroforestry systems in coffee production in Burundi.

Overcoming existing patterns of cultivation which are not adapted to climatic and soil conditions, is a challenge, although the positive effects are clear, farmers do not experience its advantages immediately.

After the successful implementation of a pilot project with two cooperatives and lessons learned the project is now extended to two cooperatives more converting to organic, but 13 more to establish agroforestry systems, the backbone for organic coffee production. The challenge is how to mainstream the experience within the cooperatives.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: agroforestry systems, Coffee production, multi-stakeholder approach

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

Session 12: Knowledge and innovation

OWC2020-STA-550

"PUBLISH OR PERISH" – INTENSIFYING AND QUALIFYING SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE RESEARCH (ISO FAR)

Anne-Kristin Løes¹, Gerold Rahmann^{*2} and The International Board of Directors of ISO FAR

¹Norwegian Centre for Organic Agriculture (NORSØK), Tingvoll, Norway, ²Institute of Organic Farming, Thünen institute, Westerau, Germany

Summary: Organic farming systems are dependent on adapted and relevant science and research. ISO FAR is a network and membership organisation for scientists active in research to develop organic farming systems. Our scientific journal *Organic Agriculture*, published by Springer since 2011, is a crucial tool for communication and increased quality of our efforts.

ISO FAR also supports and co-arranges scientific conferences, such as the OWC science forums. ISO FAR arranged a pre-conference to the OWC2020 to encourage more scientists and other stakeholders to produce and submit relevant, high-quality papers for peer-review and publishing in the journal *Organic Agriculture*.

During that event, we exchange experiences in publishing research and develop ideas for how to increase the volume and quality of published papers relevant for organic farming and growing. The output of this communication will be shared with interested stakeholders by an oral presentation in the OWC Stakeholder forum.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: International Society of Organic Agriculture Research ISO FAR, journal, peer-review, research, scientific paper

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 2 - Guide the growth dynamic of organics

OWC2020-STA-563

OVERCOMING SOCIO-TECHNICAL LOCK-INS OF ORGANIC CEREAL PRODUCTION IN EUROPE: HOW TO FOSTER AND SUSTAIN MULTI-ACTOR GRASSROOTS INITIATIVES AS DRIVERS OF TRANSITION

Amaury Beaugendre¹, Lucas Van den Abeele², Marjolein Visser¹, Riccardo Bocci³, Raphaël Boutsen⁴, Véronique Chable⁵, Emmanuelle Escarnot⁶, Isabelle Goldringer⁷, Noémie Maughan¹, Estelle Serpolay⁸

¹Agroecology Lab, Université Libre de Bruxelles, Brussels, ²Brouwerij 3 Fonteinen, Lot, Belgium, ³Rete Semi Rurali, Scandicci, Italy, ⁴Biowallonie, Namur, Belgium, ⁵UMR BAGAP, INRA, Le Rheu, France, ⁶Unité Amélioration des espèces et biodiversité, CRA-W, Gembloux, Belgium, ⁷UMR GQE - Le Moulon, INRA, Gif-sur-Yvette, ⁸ITAB, Le Rheu, France

Summary: A major constraint hindering organic sector growth lies in the incompatibilities between actors, technologies and institutions across a food system. Therefore, multi-actor grassroots initiatives have a key role to play in reconfiguring food systems. However, those come with a series of challenges of their own, which can be hard to overcome in the absence of external support (e.g.: funding, coordination structure, etc.).

With this exchange session, which will take the form of a World Café, we hope to gain insight on how these challenges can be faced in order to both foster and sustain such initiatives.

To anchor this discussion in real problematics, we studied multiple cases of such initiatives around the common issue of organic cereal production in Europe. From these case studies, we drew three transversal discussion axes: coordination, funding and deep socio-technical lock-ins.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: cereals, Lock-ins, multi-actor projects, Participatory approach

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

OWC2020-STA-622

A SERIOUS-GAME TO FOSTER TRANSITION TO SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS REGARDING SOIL HEALTH MANAGEMENT BASED ON A PROVENCAL MARKET GARDENING CASE STUDY.

Yann Boulestreau*^{1,2}, Marion Casagrande^{1,3}, Mireille Navarrete¹

¹INRA Ecodeveloppement, Avignon, ²ADEME, Angers, ³ITAB, Saint-Marcel-lès-Valence, France

Summary: We will present a serious-game that simulates the role food system plays in soil health management. When playing this game, the participants discover the mechanisms fostering unsustainable soil health management by organic (and non-organic) vegetable farmers. These mechanisms arise from the different stakeholders' behavior. Using a role-game, we make the participants act as one of the stakeholder.

Then, we make them **live** in a short time how unsustainable soil health management can emerge and which strategies can be developed to overcome the mechanisms responsible for it. Those mechanisms and strategies are then discussed with all participants based on the game experience.

Therefore, the game is a tool that can be used to inspire stakeholders and foster sustainable food system development, including guiding the growth of the organic sector. This participatory method fosters stakeholder engagement, interactions and inclusivity.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: agroecology, Food system, market-gardening, participatory workshops, serious-game, Soil health

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

OWC2020-STA-648

EXTENSION AND ADVISORY SERVICE NEEDS OF STARTUPS AND ESTABLISHED ORGANIC FARMERS IN INDIA-THE CHALLENGES AND WAYFORWARD

Mahesh Chander¹

¹Division of Extension Education, Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Bareilly, India

Summary: Many youths in India are now joining organic start-up landscape, supported by government schemes and collaboration of private sector and NGOs. The organic farmers at various stages viz some already exporting organic products, some in-conversion & some willing to switch-over to organic agriculture were interviewed.

They were having varying needs, requirements and potential for not only growing-up as organic producers, exporters but also actors in the organic agriculture value chains.

Some youths were producing and marketing organic inputs for organic farmers, while many were taking up ventures on cow-dung, vermiculture and waste to wealth type of projects. This paper shares success stories of organic farmers while presenting the challenges and opportunities before the start-ups.

How the Extension and Advisory Services can improve their capacities to cater to the needs of various categories of farmers and startups for information on sustainable organic agricultural practices, will be discussed while interacting with the participating stakeholders.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Extension and advisory services, startups, livestock

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

OWC2020-STA-730

WHICH TRICKS FOR DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR ORGANIC PRODUCTION

Claire Delaunay¹, Emeline Defossez², Marie-Pierre Cassagnes² and Project managers of VEGEPOLYS VALLEY association

¹VEGEPOLYS VALLEY, Saint Pol de Léon, ²VEGEPOLYS VALLEY, Angers, France

Summary: We would like to propose a presentation on the topic: **WHICH TRICKS FOR DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR ORGANIC PRODUCTION?**

The aim of this presentation will be to share knowledge and good practices for innovative multi-actors projects, with a particular focus on solutions for organic productions. The presentation will focus on one theme: Inspire people to take action and move toward sustainability.

Indeed, VEGEPOLYS VALLEY can inspire participants to take action by presenting projects which already have developed sustainable solutions for organic production.

Sharing experiences about these projects will help participants to identify success keys for their future projects. To sum up the sessions, some recommendations might be given to encourage the participants to undertake collaborative private-public actions.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: good practices for innovative projects, , innovative solutions, multi-actor projects , plant production, sharing experiences

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 2 - Guide the growth dynamic of organics

Session 13: Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-269

ORGANIC AQUACULTURE

Giuseppe Lembo¹ on behalf of IFOAM Aquaculture Forum, David Gould², Chris Atkinson³, Alex Warrington³ and IFOAM Aquaculture Forum

¹COISPA Tecnologia & Ricerca, Bari, Italy, ²FoodChain ID, Fairfield, IA 52556, United States, ³Soil Association, Bristol, United Kingdom

Summary: Global consumption of aquaculture products continues to grow, accounting for 17% of total animal protein consumed globally in 2015. Global aquaculture production (excluding aquatic plants) reached 80 million tonnes in 2016, representing 47% of total global fish production and 53% if non-food uses (including reduction to fishmeal and fish oil) are excluded.

Including aquatic plants, aquaculture production totalled 110.2 million tons, of which just over 0.5% was organic. Although the organic segment remains very small compared to non-organic, consumption of organic fish and seafood in the EU has grown by 49% in the period 2013-2017.

Organic principles may be applied to aquaculture systems, as General Assembly of IFOAM Organics International voted in 2017. Organic has an opportunity to impact this growing food sector, but it needs to embody the Principles to the fullest extent whilst being practically achievable. Impact measurement and knowledge sharing are essential to ensure success.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Health & Welfare, Ecosystem impact, Product quality, Consumer interest/acceptance

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 2 - Guide the growth dynamic of organics

Session 14: Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-1439

SHARED SURVEILLANCE AND REGIONAL ADAPTIVENESS UNDER INTERNATIONAL ORGANIC STANDARDS

Carolin Moeller*¹, Karen Mapusua² and Jim Pierce, Litia Kirwin, Beate Huber are already a part. Working group is open for new contributions

¹NASAA Certified Organic, Stirling, Australia, ²SPC, SUVA, Fiji

Summary: Group Certification is based on the concept of shared surveillance to ensure true compliance to organic standards and regulation.

Group certification under organic regulations and standards was introduced as a certification product over 20 years ago. In 2003 IFOAM International Organics set up the first guidelines on how to set up a grower group and its mandatory Internal Control System and how certification bodies shall certify these grower groups.

In 2019, certification bodies & grower groups called for reassessing procedures and evaluating potential of improvement for grower group's attainable certification requirements.

Driving factors

- global lack in traceability and true procedures in group certification.
- compliance conflicts due to particular regional, socio-agricultural set ups of groups.
- Approval for group certification within the EU

Through trialling training the need for regional adaptiveness of regulations/requirements has emerged

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Grower Groups, Internal Control Systems, Pacific islands, Shared Surveillance

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 2 - Guide the growth dynamic of organics

Session 15: Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-619

CORE ORGANIC NETWORK: 15 YEARS OF EUROPEAN TRANSNATIONAL RESEARCH IN ORGANIC FOOD AND FARMING

Ivana Trkulja¹, Elena Capolino²

¹ERA-NET CORE Organic, International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems (ICROFS), Tjele, Denmark, ²Department of European and international policies and rural development, Ministry of agricultural food and forestry policies, Florence, Italy

Summary: ERA-NET CORE Organic (CO) - Coordination of European Transnational Research in Organic Food and Farming Systems - proposes an interactive exchange session to illustrate value, benefits and challenges of the ERA-NET network supporting transnational organic research in a broader European Research Areas (ERA) context.

The European network of agriculture ministries and research councils was established in 2004. It presently includes 27 European partners gathered under the main aim to fund transnational organic research. By joining the forces, the network supports focused and coordinated research and innovation efforts, covering the most important challenges along the organic value chains.

The Exchange Session at the OWC 2020 will **present the network's specific transnational working methods** (involving public funders and stakeholders from the organic sector) and **the results from the multi-actor research projects covering themes** (cropping systems, livestock and food processing).

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: cropping systems and livestock, Europe, Multi-actor approach, Network of public funders and organic sector stakeholders, Transnational organic research

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 2 - Guide the growth dynamic of organics

Session 16: Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-1099

CERTIFICATION AS A GROUP OF OPERATORS IN EUROPE: REQUIREMENTS, BEST PRACTICE AND CHALLENGES

Florentine Meinshausen¹ , Emanuele Busacca * ² , Beate Huber³ , Joelle Katto-Andrighetto⁴ , Toralf Richter³ , Meriam Ghedira⁵ , Patricia Pugliese⁶ and IFOAM-FiBL Group Certification in EU

¹ Consultant for IFOAM-Organics International, Zurich, Switzerland, ² IFOAM EU, Brussels, Belgium, ³ FiBL, Frick,

Switzerland, ⁴ IFOAM-Organic International, Bonn, Germany, ⁵ IFOAM EU, Brussels, Switzerland, ⁶ CIHEAM Bari, Bari, Italy

Summary: The new EU Organic Regulation (EU) 2018/848 (Basic Act) sets new rules for the certification of grower groups worldwide which will be enforced from 2021 on forwards. For the first time, groups of small farms within the EU can become certified as a “group of operators” according to criteria set down in the Basic Act and further developed under the secondary legislation which is, at the time of submission, still under discussion by the Commission and Member States.

The workshop explains the new regulatory requirements for such European “groups of operators” in detail and shares learnings from international implementation of group certification as the basis to develop with the participants practical ideas where certification as a group of operators in the EU is meaningful, best practices to aim for and how to get started.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Group certification, Group of Operators, New EU Regulation

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 2 - Guide the growth dynamic of organics

Session 17: Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-1299

HOW TO INCREASE PRODUCTION AND USE OF ORGANIC SEED? STATE OF THE ART AND BEST PRACTICES

Freya Schaefer^{*1}, Maaïke Raaijmakers², Stefano Orsini³, Kristina Hubbard⁴, Francesco Solfanelli⁵, Eva Winter¹, Bram Moeskops⁶

¹Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frankfurt am Main, Germany, ²Bionext, the Dutch foundation for organic food and farming, Ede, Netherlands, ³Organic Research Centre, Hamstead Marshall, United Kingdom, ⁴Organic Seed Alliance, Port Townsend, United States, ⁵Università Politecnica delle Marche, Ancona, Italy, ⁶IFOAM EU Group, Brussels, Belgium

Summary: Seeds are the foundation of farming. Therefore, organic production should start with organic seed. Using organic seed is mandatory according to the European organic regulation, but untreated conventional seed is still used to varying an extent in different countries.

This is allowed by the regulation if there is a lack of organic seed on the market. Continuous use of this derogation, however, is a barrier for seed companies to invest in the production of organic seed and to put more seed on the market.

The aims of the Workshop are to: 1) Present the state of the art of organic seed production and use in Europe and the US, based on the outcomes of the surveys conducted in Europe within the European Research project LIVESEED and in the US by the Organic Seed Alliance (OSA); 2) Present incentives in place and good practice examples, and 3) discuss/identify with the WS participants sustainable forms of incentives for the future development of the organic seed sector.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Best practices, organic seed use, production of organic seed

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 2 - Guide the growth dynamic of organics

Session 18: Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-674

HOW REGIONAL KNOWLEDGE HUBS DISSEMINATE VALIDATED KNOWLEDGE ON ORGANIC AGRICULTURE APPLYING A MULTI STAKEHOLDER APPROACH

Mara Lindtner¹, Angela Coetzee², David Amudavi³, Alex Mutungi⁴, Assane Gueye⁵, Dorith von Behaim^{*1}, Ibrahima Seck⁶, Mariam Sow⁷

¹GIZ, Eschborn, Germany, ²Sustainability Institute, Stellenbosch, South Africa, ³Biovision Africa Trust, ⁴EOA-I, Nairobi, Kenya, ⁵Agrecol Afrique, ⁶FENAB, Thiès, ⁷ENDA-ProNat, Dakar, Senegal

Summary: To alleviate the lack of knowledge many farmers are facing, the GIZ project Knowledge Centre for Organic Agriculture in Africa (KCOA) together with African partner organizations is establishing knowledge hubs in North, East, West and Southern Africa for the collection, validation and dissemination of relevant traditional and innovative knowledge.

The session will give participants the possibility to exchange and connect with the implementing partners of the four regional hubs and with EOA-I on a continental level. Leading topics of the session will be the knowledge management approach, the dissemination channels, specific knowledge needs for OA, the knowledge validation process and the importance of the involvement of a wide range of stakeholders in these processes.

The combination of presentations and the interactive method of the World Café will allow participants to obtain interesting information about the project and bring in their own experiences in the discussions.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: None

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 6 - Commit together to the health of soils, food, people and of the planet

Session 19: Certification

OWC2020-STA-339

SHARING THE OUTCOMES OF THE PRE-CONFERENCE "30 YEARS OF PGS DEVELOPMENT: A ROOT AND BRANCH APPRAISAL"

Federica Varini¹, Sylvaine Lemeilleur Lemeilleur*²

¹IFOAM-Organics International, Bonn, Germany, ²Environnements et Sociétés, CIRAD, Montpellier, France

Summary: After 15 years from the first international workshop on alternative certification in Brazil, IFOAM-Organics International, Nature & Progrès and CIRAD organise the preconference "30 years of PGS development: a root and branch appraisal".

This event creates the opportunity to gather once again international PGS initiatives, practitioners and experts to stocktake on current PGS development and setting new targets to improve PGS worldwide.

It is expected that a global declaration, supported by PGS stakeholders from all over the world will be prepared during this event and will be adopted at the conference, providing a vision for the future development of PGS, rooted on their importance for the organic movement and their contribution to position organic agriculture as an agent of change.

This session aims at sharing the declaration and other outcomes of the pre-conference within the Congress.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Alternative Certification, Food Sovereignty, Innovation, Organic 3.0, PGS

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

OWC2020-STA-1320

LE SYSTÈME PARTICIPATIF DE GARANTIE AU BÉNIN APRÈS CINQ ANNÉES DE MISE EN OEUVRE: ÉTATS DES LIEUX ET PERSPECTIVES

Bodjrenou Delphine¹, DEGUENON Edgar², VODOUHE Simplicie³

¹ATLANTIQUE, OBEPAB, ²ATLANTIQUE, HORTITECHS DEVELOPMENTS, COTONOU,

³ATLANTIQUE, FSA/UAC, ABOMEY-CALAVI, Benin

Summary: In Benin, the implementation of organic certification SPG was supported by Helvétas Benin. This has gone through several stages, including consulting stakeholders, designing and validating tools, setting up certification bodies, organizing field surveys, awarding certificates and mentions, evaluating certification device, etc. It is a tool for facilitating the emergence of organic local markets for all budgets.

It is also a way of lightening long-term costs of international certification because its application is less expensive compared to third-party certification.

In the case of Benin, the adoption of the SPG certification facilitates the traceability of organic products cultivated by small producers, reinforces the guarantee on products and opens new markets of sale to the cooperatives and companies that are involved.

The Participatory Guarantee System (PGS) is a locally anchored quality assurance that certifies productions on the basis of the active participation for a local trust

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Bénin, Défis, Perspectives, SPG,

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

OWC2020-STA-850

ORGANIC CERTIFICATION IS EXPELLING SMALL PRODUCERS FROM THE MARKET?

Jeronimo Pruijn*¹, Nelson Camilo Melo Maya² on behalf of Board SPP Global and SPP Global Board of Directors

¹Executive Direction, SPP Global, Mexico City, Mexico, ²Presidency, SPP Global, Popayán, Colombia

Summary: Small producers and, particularly, small producers' organizations from around the world have been key in the historical development of the organic production practices and market in different parts of the world. As the organic market started to grow, also the amount of regulations grew. Both for organic production itself, as well as for the certification and accreditation-processes.

Small producers in several countries have dedicated numerous efforts to be part of the discussions and processes around the development of these regulations around the world. Particularly small producers' organizations have struggled to get group certification recognized, which has not been an easy task in the past.

At present, the new EU Organic Regulations 2021 and secondary regulations, still being formulated, are putting limitations on group certification, which can imply an significant increase of costs of certification for these groups, without clear framework for accreditation of organic certifiers.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Accreditation, Certification, economic feasibility, Eu organic legislation, Market Access, Small producers

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 4 - Adapt on climate change and reduce the carbon footprint

OWC2020-STA-999

ORGANIC PASIFIKA CERTIFICATION, LEVERAGING FOR ENHANCED RESILIENCE

Clement Gandet¹, Julie Ferrand²

¹Climat Change and Environmental Sustainability Division, Pacific Community (SPC), ²Chambre d'agriculture NC, Noumea, New Caledonia

Summary: The Pacific Community has developed a Pacific Organic Standard with its Organic Pasifika label, adopted by all countries and territories in the region. The PROTEGE project funded by the European Union and implemented by the Pacific Community (SPC) pursues the goal of supporting sustainable and resilient development in the face of climate change in European Pacific territories.

Several PROTEGE actions aim to promote resilient agricultural practices and biodiversity in agrosystems, through recognition through organic certification of the farmers who implement them. This certification has as specificity to rely on a standard valuing the practices, the traditional knowledge of the Pacific islanders.

Finally, its method of obtaining through the participatory guarantee system involves the mobilization of the community in the process of recognizing farmers engaged in practices that ultimately benefit the entire population (quality food, soil health, biodiversity, ...)

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Carbon sequestration, climate change, climate resilience, organic certification, Pacific islands

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 2 - Guide the growth dynamic of organics

OWC2020-STA-882

ORGANIC FOOD INTEGRITY & AUTHENTICITY: A KEY CHALLENGE FOR SUSTAINABLE GROWTH

Jean-François Morin*¹ and TOFoo project

¹Eurofins, NANTES CEDEX 3, France

Summary: As acknowledged by the prospective study Organic 3.0, there is a need for an increased level of authenticity and transparency in the organic sector.

A multi-stakeholder initiative called True Organic Food (TOFoo) has the ambition to develop innovative analytical tools to face this authenticity challenge.

This initiative will result in increased consumer trust in the organic production system, thus in sustainable economic growth. The involvement of all the organic stakeholders will be a key success factor.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: authentication, dairy product, Integrity, plant-based food, Transparency

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 5 - Foster biodiversity and diversity at multiple scales

Session 20: Genetic diversity

OWC2020-STA-1194

DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE SEED SYSTEMS FOR ORGANIC FARMING

Livia Ortolani¹, Riccardo Bocci¹, Bettina Bussi¹, Salvatore Ceccarelli¹, Matteo Petitti¹ and all Rete Semi Rurali members

¹Rete Semi Rurali, Scandicci (FI), Italy

Summary: Biodiversity is a fundamental component of organic farming systems and the base for resilience of organic food systems.

Organic farmers' knowledge and experience, in interaction with all other organic chain actors can be a resource to foster biodiversity at multiple scale. Local collective experiences of seed networks represent interesting experiences of multi-actor networks aiming at conserving and facilitating the use of agrobiodiversity developed with a participatory and bottom up approach.

However, the formality required by the organic certification is considered often a barrier to include such experiences within the organic sector. This paper presents the experience of Rete Semi Rurali in bringing genetic heterogeneous material developed with a long-term interaction with actors embedded in the seed system, including public institutions all the way to organic seed certification and direct marketing of organic seed.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Seed systems, organic seed, community agrobiodiversity management, participatory and decentralized breeding

OWC 2020 – Stakeholder Forum

Topic 4 – Adapt on climate change and reduce the carbon footprint

OWC2020-STA-1198

BRESOV (2018-2022): A EUROPEAN PROJECT DEDICATED TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF RESILIENT AND SUSTAINABLE ORGANIC VEGETABLE PRODUCTION (TOMATO, BROCCOLI, SNAP BEAN)

Sarah Danan*¹, Céline Hamon¹

¹VEGENOV, Saint Pol de Léon, France

Summary: Organic product demand is significantly increasing world-wide, especially in Europe. In parallel, global climate change urges the need of developing resilient agricultural systems.

The European BRESOV project (Breeding for Resilient, Efficient and Sustainable Organic Vegetable production, 2018-2022) addresses these challenges in the sector of vegetable production through two levers at the breeding level: exploiting genetic diversity, and creating a pipeline for crop improvement, including the production of high-quality organic seeds.

Three economically important crops have been chosen as models: tomato, broccoli and snap bean. BRESOV involves twenty-two partners located in different eco-geographical areas of European countries, EU associated countries and third countries in Asia.

The project follows a multi-actor approach involving academia, industry and farmers to deliver improved germplasm for European varieties adapted to the challenges of future organic vegetable production.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: breeding, Europe, Multi-actor approach, Organic agriculture production, resilience, vegetables

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 3 - Develop organic and sustainable plant and animal production, food and non-food systems

OWC2020-STA-1201

A COOPERATIVE ORIGINAL EXPERIENCE TO IMPROVE WINTER BREAD WHEAT ORGANIC BREEDING STRATEGIES

Bernard Rolland¹, Jérôme Auzanneau², Jean-Pierre Bouchet³, Pierre De Contes⁴, Guylain Degryse⁵, Laurence Fontaine⁶, Emmanuel Heumez⁷, Berengère Millot⁵, Gregory Moreau⁵, Maddalena Moretti⁸, Rémi Perronne¹, Grégoire Rouyer⁴, François-Xavier Oury⁹

¹BAP, INRA, LE RHEU, ²Agri-Obtentions, Orsonville, ³UBIOS, Maisse, ⁴BIOCER, Le Plessis grohan, ⁵COCEBI, Nitry, ⁶ITAB, Angers, ⁷BAP, INRA, Estrées-Mons, ⁸Bio en Normandie, Val de Reuil, ⁹BAP, INRA, Clermont-Ferrand, France

Summary: After 20 years of screening and breeding combined in two different cropping systems, i.e. very low inputs and organic systems, six pure lines obtained by INRA have been registered in the Official French Catalogue with the special mention « organic farming ».

From 2012 to 2020, for the second step of bread wheat breeding initiative, two historical farmer's cooperatives were associated in a so-called "cooperative selection process".

This successful working process was possible with the support of the entire agricultural organic sector associated in the initiative coordinated by ITAB.

This collaboration boosts the genetic progress and facilitates the exchange of new options and goals among farmers, agronomists and breeders for designing more adapted and efficient strategies in plant breeding for organic.

Keywords: bread wheat, Cooperative, FARMERS, plant breeding, varieties

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

OWC2020-STA-1238

OLD PROBLEMS NEW SOLUTIONS: BROKERING AGROBIODIVERSITY MANAGEMENT ENTERPRISES IN CUBA

Humberto Rios Labrada¹, Juan Ceballos Müller², Julia Wright¹

¹Centre for Agroecology, Water and Resilience, Coventry University, Coventry, United Kingdom,

²iCRA, Wageningen, Netherlands

Summary: In many places of the world low input agriculture is still predominant; therefore farmers are forced to seek varieties with the capacity of adapting to the particular environment of their farm. This situation also requires a decentralised and participatory seed diffusion model connected to agroecological practices.

In Cuba due to the critical situation of seed supply, Agrobiodiversity Management Enterprises were initiated with the purpose to help in developing a decentralised demand driven seed sector.

This paper describes a pilot endeavour, in which farmer champions and professional plant breeders are taking the next step towards a market driven business model.

Despite the socioeconomic situation in Cuba is unique, the collaborative business prototypes designed between public researchers and small farmers could give some clues to other countries where the public research sector is still in place.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Inclusive business, agrobiodiversity, participation

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 3 - Develop organic and sustainable plant and animal production, food and non-food systems

OWC2020-STA-731

CO-DEVELOPMENT OF A PARTICIPATORY VARIETY TRIAL NETWORK FOR DIVERSIFIED ORGANIC VEGETABLE FARMERS

Charlotte Giard Laliberte^{* 1,1}, François Gendreau-Martineau¹, Caroline Poirier^{2, 3}, Helen Jensen⁴

¹CETAB+ (Centre de Recherche en Agriculture Biologique), Victoriaville, ²CAPÉ-Coopérative pour l'Agriculture de Proximité et Écologique, Montréal, ³Ferme Croque-Saisons, Lingwick, ⁴USC Canada, Montréal, Canada

Summary: The use of vegetable varieties suitable for organic vegetable production is one of the key elements of a farm's success. Although the need for structured variety trials had been identified in the past by vegetable farmers in Quebec, no such endeavour existed yet until our project started in 2018.

Multiple actors of the organic farming sector were thus gathered to develop a collective solution to fulfill a need that the seed industry did not adequately address. Concretely, we initiated a participatory variety trial network that aims to be run by and for the organic diversified vegetable farmers of Quebec.

We used the "mother-daughter" trials design to facilitate knowledge transfer between farmers and researchers. After two years, where two variety trials – one on storage carrots and one on watermelon- were conducted by fifteen participating farmers and CETAB+, we want to share the successes and challenges encountered while developing the network.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: "Mother-daughter" trial design, Participatory research, Variety trial

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

Session 21: Exchange session

OWC2020-STA-714

CAPITALISING ON SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE TO EFFECTIVELY COMMUNICATE AND PROMOTE THE SUSTAINABILITY OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS

Isabella Gusenbauer*¹, Olivia Keller², Richard Petrasek¹

¹Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL, Vienna, Austria, ²sfs Sustainable Food Systems GmbH, Frick, Switzerland

Summary: In a global and interconnected food system, complex and detailed information is needed to make informed choices with regard to sustainability. Furthermore, the term sustainability is often used in an inconsistent way.

There seems to be a gap between companies, farms and agricultural associations that evaluate their sustainability performance in a comparable way and consumers who find themselves unable to judge how sustainable a given agricultural commodity or food product really is.

At the same time significant research has been undertaken to assess the sustainability of food systems, but still these efforts and results do not seem to close this gap.

Evidently the question arises; whether and how businesses along the food value chain can capitalise on scientific knowledge to effectively communicate and promote the sustainability of agricultural products and services.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: None

FRANCE

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES

AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE

www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

Session 25: Global and multi-actors

OWC2020-STA-1181

THE MULTI-ACTOR PPILOW EUROPEAN PROJECT: A PARTICIPATIVE APPROACH TO CO-BUILD INNOVATIONS FOR WELFARE IMPROVEMENT IN ORGANIC PIG AND POULTRY FARMS

Cristina Micheloni¹, An Jamart², Martina Re¹, Laura Van Vooren², Jarkko Niemi³, Frank Tuytens⁴, T. Bas Rodenburg⁵, Antoine Roinsard⁶, Sanna Steinfeldt⁷, Petra Thobe⁸, Riccardo Carelli⁹, Marlene Sciarretta⁹, Claire Bonnefous¹⁰, Pauline Bodin¹¹, Andrea Rosati⁹, Henry Van den Brand¹², Lucia Rocchi¹³, Maxime Reverchon¹⁴, Virginie Decruyenaere¹⁵, José Wavreille¹⁵, Grete Brunsgaard¹⁶, Stefaan Depraetere¹⁷, Katia Grenier¹⁸, Jan Vanggaard¹⁹, Raffaella Ponzio²⁰, Vanessa Guesdon²¹, Hélène Leruste²¹, Keith Walley²², Vasile Cozma²³, Elisabeth Le Bihan-Duval¹⁰, Ricarda Engberg⁷, Sophie Réhault-Godbert¹⁰, Lisa Baldinger²⁴, Mirjan Thys⁴, Armelle Prunier²⁵, Elodie Merlot²⁵, Céline Tallet²⁵, Lucile Montagne²⁵, Laurianne Canario²⁶, Elsa Delanoue²⁷, Valérie Courboulay²⁸, Jonathan Hercule²⁷, Christine Leterrier³⁰, Joselle Latchoumia³¹, Laura Warin²⁹, Anne Collin^{*10}

¹AIAB, Bova Marina (RC), Italy, ²BioForum Vlaanderen, Regine Beerplein, Belgium, ³Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke), Seinäjoki, Finland, ⁴Animal Sciences Unit, Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), Melle, Belgium, ⁵Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Utrecht University, Utrecht, The Netherlands, ⁶ITAB, Angers, France, ⁷Department of Animal Science, Aarhus University, Tjele, Denmark, ⁸Institute of Farm Economics, Thünen Institute, Braunschweig, Germany, ⁹EAAP, Roma, Italy, ¹⁰INRAE, Université de Tours, BOA, Nouzilly, France, ¹¹ACTA, Paris, France, ¹²Adaptation Physiology Group, Wageningen University and Research, Wageningen, The Netherlands, ¹³Department of Agricultural, Environmental and Food Science, University of Perugia, Perugia, Italy, ¹⁴SYSAF, Nouzilly, France, ¹⁵Production and Sectors Department, Walloon Agricultural Research Centre, Gembloux, Belgium, ¹⁶Fermentationexperts AS, Bække, Denmark, ¹⁷Circular Organics nv, Turnhout, Belgium, ¹⁸CNRS, LAAS, Toulouse, France, ¹⁹Vanggaard Staldmontage, Brønderslev, Denmark, ²⁰Slow Food Biodiversity, Firenze, Italy, ²¹JUNIA, CASE, Lille, France, ²²Harper-Adams University, Newport, United Kingdom, ²³USAMV Cluj, Cluj-Napoca, Romania, ²⁴Institute of Organic Farming, Thünen Institute, Westerau, Germany, ²⁵PEGASE, INRAE, Institut Agro, Saint-Gilles, France, ²⁶INRAE, Université de Toulouse, ENVT, GenPhySE, Castanet Tolosan, France, ²⁷ITAVI, IDELE, IFIP, Paris, France, ²⁸IFIP La Motte au Vicomte, Le Rheu, France, ²⁹ITAVI, Nouzilly, France, ³⁰INRAE, CNRS, IFCE, Université de Tours, PRC, Nouzilly, France, ³¹INRAE Transfert, Paris, France

Summary: The PPILOW project aims to co-construct through a multi-actor approach innovations to improve the welfare of poultry and pigs reared in organic and low-input outdoor farming systems.

The first originality of PPILOW is the participatory approach, involving all actors of the production chain from farmers to consumers, citizens, scientists and policy makers, for proposing and studying welfare improvement levers. The second originality of the project is to provide a combination of practical solutions for welfare improvement that can be applied on a pan-European basis with specific adjustments depending on citizen's expectations and the

target market. More precisely, PPILOW co-creates with end-users, gathered in connected National Practitioner Groups (NPG), welfare self-assessment tools, innovative breeding and rearing strategies and techniques for improving the welfare of animals by avoiding physical damage (piglet castration or beak trimming in poultry) and the elimination of one day-old layer male chicks, favouring positive behaviours, and improving health and robustness in both species.

The multi-actor approach consists in gathering in NPG representatives of selection firms, feed producers, consumer associations, retailers, advisers, processors, scientists and farmers in several countries. The groups are facilitated by PPILOW project partners making the links between NPG at European level, transferring scientific information, interacting with partners engaged in animal experiments and co-creating innovations rising from NPG-specific demands. Especially they will contribute to the co-building and testing of welfare self-assessment tools, target specific means of improving welfare, co-design the protocols, test innovations on farm and disseminate the results, with in turn insights in scientific results and methods, and inputs from other NPG for reinforcing the value of the expected outcomes.

The innovative solutions are currently investigated experimentally and the most promising ones will be tested on-farm after discussions within the NPG. Multicriteria analyses of the most effective breeding and rearing strategies will then be performed to evaluate their economic, social and environmental impacts based on the 'One Welfare' concept embracing sustainability goals with specific emphasis on animal and human welfare. Business models will be created for the use of high-quality products issued from the adoption of PPILOW strategies.

Finally, to ensure the rapid uptake of the project results by end-users, appropriate dissemination activities will be developed (such as training, on-farm demonstrations, and digital videos from field partners etc.). The facilitation of change will be managed through the close involvement of the PPILOW's participative groups throughout the EU.

Funding: The PPILOW project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement N°816172.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: multi-actor projects, organic, pigs, poultry, welfare

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 3 - Develop organic and sustainable plant and animal production, food and non-food systems

OWC2020-STA-1267

MILPA PROGRAM HOW A PARTNERSHIP BETWEEN A PRIVATE FOOD COMPANY & ORGANIC INSTITUTIONAL STAKEHOLDERS ACCELERATE DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC REGENERATIVE AGRICULTURE IN FRANCE

Pierre-Antoine Morel¹, Marion Casagrande², Samuel Frois³

¹Blédina, LIMONEST, ²ITAB, ³FNAB, PARIS, France

Summary: In 2018, Blédina launched its first range of organic products. Driven by the common ambition of a growing sustainable organic sector, Blédina, FNAB and ITAB, allied their knowledge and expertise to build up the MILPA project; a program that supports both organic conversion and sustainable crop management for fruits and vegetables French farmers.

The MILPA program is to enhance farmers competitiveness and economic stability by fostering regenerative agricultural practices that will reinforce baby grade standards and improve soil quality.

The program has been designed on 3 pillars:

1. A technical and economical training program throughout the conversion process
2. A research program for developing and implementing innovative practices to improve soil quality
3. Disseminate learnings and technical knowledge to all ecosystems

This program is the result of a complementary stakeholders alliance; Blédina (leader and funding), FNAB & ITAB (technical actors), Danone Ecosystem Fund (Dotation fund).

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Communication, local sourcing, partnership, regenerative agriculture, soil health

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 3 - Develop organic and sustainable plant and animal production, food and non-food systems

OWC2020-STA-489

ORGANIC PROCESSING METHODS – THE WAY FORWARD

Alexander Beck¹, Flavio Paoletti², Toralf Richter³, Katrin Zander⁴

¹Assoziation ökologischer Lebensmittelhersteller (AÖL) e.V., Bad Brückenau, Germany, ²Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria - CREA, Rome, Italy, ³Forschungsinstitut für biologischen Landbau - FibL, Frick, Switzerland, ⁴Thünen-Institut für Marktanalyse, Braunschweig, Germany

Summary: The project ProOrg aims at developing guidelines for organic food processing. While inputs are regulated, processing technologies are not.

The guidelines will give organic food processors and other stakeholders orientation in developing and using modern food processing technologies.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: guidelines, organic processing, processing technologies

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 6 - Commit together to the health of soils, food, people and of the planet

OWC2020-STA-711

MINDFUL EATING: A FIRST STEP TOWARDS A HEALTHY FUTURE

Jasmin Peschke*¹

¹Nutrition Department, Section for Agriculture, Dornach, Switzerland

Summary: With the theme of the World Food Day in 2019 "Our Actions are Our Future" the FAO claimed a change of mind and behaviour to face the problem of malnutrition in the world. Everyone was asked to start thinking about the daily diet.

As healthy food comes from healthy soil everyone is called up to take responsibility and act in the sense of a sustainable future and not wait for others to do so. An individual first step is practicing mindful eating: the senses are trained and perceptions are enhanced. Empathy and interest develop.

This means people care for where food comes from and under what conditions it is produced and traded. Relationships, partnership and respect are cultivated. These are key properties for a healthy future.

Everyone can start with mindfulness without precondition and no matter at which point in the value-added chain he/her is located. Mindful eating contributes to fulfill SDGs and meets IFOAM attributes for the Organic Food System Programme.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Connectedness, Health of Soil, Food, People and the Planet, Mindful eating, Organic Food System Program, Sustainable Development Goals, Value-added Chain

Session 26: Network

OWC2020-SCI-1095

THE ONLINE PLATFORM “ORGANIC FARM KNOWLEDGE”

Helga Willer*¹, Bram Moeskops², Antoine Roinsard³, Andreas Basler¹, Laura Kemper¹, Ilse A. Rasmussen⁴
¹Extension, Training and Communication, FiBL, Frick, Switzerland, ²IFOAM EU, Brussels, Belgium, ³ITAB, Angers, France, ⁴ICROFS, Tjele, Denmark

Abstract: The complexity of organic farming requires farmers to have a very high level of knowledge and skills, but cross-border exchange on farming practices, including organic, remains limited. The Organic Farm Knowledge platform (<https://organic-farmknowledge.org/>) provides access to a wide range of tools and resources about organic farming that can help improve production, and it promotes the exchange of knowledge among farmers, farm advisors, and scientists.

The first version of the platform was built by the project OK-Net Arable, and it is now extended by OK-Net EcoFeed. Both projects are thematic networks funded under the European Union's research programme Horizon 2020. OK-Net Arable aimed to improve productivity in organic arable cropping, while OK-Net EcoFeed aims to help organic pig and poultry farmers achieve the goal of using 100% organic and regional feed.

In addition to these two projects, Organic Farm Knowledge is cooperating with several other projects to widen the knowledge base of the platform.

Keywords: communication, knowledge exchange, knowledge reservoir, organic farming practice, practice tool

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 1 - Inspire people to take action toward sustainability and best practices

OWC2020-STA-1302

THE FLEMISH ORGANIC RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGE (FORK)- NETWORK IN PRACTICE FARMERS AT THE HEART OF THE FLEMISH ORGANIC RESEARCH & KNOWLEDGE (FORK)- NETWORK

An Jamar¹, Carmen Landuyt², Lieve De Cock³

¹BioForum Vlaanderen vzw, Antwerpen, ²CCBT vzw, Kruishoutem, ³NOBL, ILVO, Merelbeke, Belgium

Summary: Exchange of experiences and tacit knowledge between farmers is at the heart of the Flemish Organic Research & Knowledge Network (FORK-network). The FORK-network consists of 3 different networks (BBN, CCBT & NOBL), closely working together to create a better coordination, cooperation and management of research and knowledge exchange for the organic food and farming sector in Flanders.

During the years, joint activities are organised, guided by the principle of co-creation: participatory research, research based on needs in the organic sector and knowledge exchange and dissemination of knowledge tailored to farmers.

We present the lessons learned and challenges which can inspire starting farmers' networks and research institutes towards more co-creation

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Co-creation, Farmersnetworks, Organic Research, Participative research

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 2 - Guide the growth dynamic of organics

OWC2020-STA-741

AGENCE BIO, A CONSULTATION PLATFORM FOR ALL ACTORS ON ALL ORGANIC ISSUES

Florent GUHL* 1, Anne BASSET2

1director, 2Agence BIO, MONTREUIL, France

Summary: Agence BIO is the national platform for the development and promotion of French organic farming.

It's a specifically French body. It has a management board comprising two government ministries and professionals from the organic sector, and its remit is to analyse data, organize organic supply chains and communicate to general and professional audiences.

Because it is not in charge of the application of organic regulations and controls, Agence BIO's activity can focus on the economic development of organic sectors and on its role as a communication channel to the general public (e.g. media, exhibitions) Given organic's healthy development in France, its role as a "discussion and consultation platform" has been strengthened for the whole range of actors – public, business, financial, non-profit associations, policymakers, and others.

This special type of organization has attracted attention from foreign actors and might be envisaged for Romania as soon as 2020, as well as in Morocco.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: consultation, DISCUSSIONS, platform

SEPTEMBER 21ST TO 27TH, 2020 IN RENNES
AT THE COUVENT DES JACOBINS • RENNES MÉTROPOLE CONFERENCE CENTRE
www.owc.ifoam.bio/2020

OWC 2020 - Stakeholder Forum

Topic 2 - Guide the growth dynamic of organics

OWC2020-STA-783

KNOWLEDGE HUB FOR ORGANIC FOOD AND FARMING

Janne Nordlund Othén¹, Maria Wivstad¹

¹Organic Food and Farming (Epok), Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Uppsala, Sweden

Summary: The need for research-based knowledge and neutral information about organic production and organic food in one place has been requested by different stakeholders in Sweden.

As a response to this demand a web-based portal is being produced by the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), in collaboration with stakeholder organisations. The portal will help organisations, companies and authorities to produce reliable information based on facts and research knowledge, and also deliver a knowledge base for policymakers.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: collaboration, information, knowledge, organic food sector

THE CO-ORGANISERS

International Federation of Agriculture Movements

French and international certification body

French national bodies and federations

French regional organic trade associations

Organic research organizations

PUBLIC PARTNERS

Financé par

OUR PARTNERS

OUR SPONSORS

Platinum

Gold

Silver

Bronze

